

SIGNAL PROCESSING OF ACOUSTIC EMISSION FOR DAMAGE IDENTIFICATION IN WOVEN COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

The acoustic emission (AE) associated with basic failure mechanisms (matrix cracking, interface fracture, fibre fracture), in woven composite materials has been studied. Test specimens are subject to three-point flexural tests for discriminate damage processes. Detection and analysis of AE used in parallel with scanning electron microscopy (SEM) has a great potential for monitoring and identifying the damage mechanisms. The results obtained has permitted to establish correlation between acoustic events and different phenomena occurring during the failure processes.

INTRODUCTION

The damage processes in composite materials subjected to mechanical loading are accompanied by emission of elastic stress waves knowing as acoustic emission. Detection and analysis of these waveforms are likely to provide information during the damage and fracture mechanisms of the materials under applied stresses. Technique of AE has been widely used for identifying some of the damage mechanisms or, in some cases, for monitoring the failure process [1,2,3]. Previous studies [4,5] based on amplitude distribution of AE performed on different type of materials have shown that this method supplies information on the damaged mechanisms. It appears that this procedure is able to provide an indication about the successive stages of the damage process, but it is still insufficient to discriminate between various AE sources when they occur simultaneously. More powerful and advanced analysis methods are required.

The principal objective of the present study is to use the signal processing of AE waveforms for providing other complementary data concerning the damage processes, as well as allowing the distinction between different phases and multiple sources of AE. The method is based on extracting some features of waveforms, and thereafter correlating them with predicted ones for possible sources using theoretical and experimental results of previous studies [5,6].

As far as the details of waveforms acquisition and analysis are concerned, the realised procedures are given in the following sections.

EXPERIMENT CONDITIONS

MATERIALS PRESENTATION

The study concerns three-point flexural tests are performed on two types of material. The used specimens are two composite materials which are reinforced by a E-glass balanced woven from Vetrotex Company. The both employed resins are vinyl-ester made by Dow Chemical

Company. The first one is ductile called Derakane XD 8084.05, while the later is more brittle knowing as Derakane D 470.36.

Mechanical tests are conducted on specimens of 10 mm x 75 mm x 3.2 mm with $l/h = 22$.

AE is monitoring during all of these tests by a transducer positioned on the specimen. The flexural tests are performed using an Instron universal static machine 1186 with a cross-head speed of 2 mm min^{-1} .

To obtain a great deal of informations for identifying damage and fracture mechanisms in composite materials, Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) observations and fractographical studies are conducted to analysis these phenomena at different selected moments during tests. However, these usual methods can reveal some defects as well as their size, but cannot evaluate their nocivity. Thus, it is necessary to obtain, in real time, information about the internal damage development of such material under applied loading. AE is a technique having a potential for the investigation of the damage-related sources in composite materials (fibre fracture, matrix cracking, interface failure, etc.).

ACOUSTIC EMISSION PROCEDURE

AE monitoring is carried out by using Dunegan Endevco-3000 instrumentation. The acoustic waveforms are detected by a piezo electric transducer (Pac Micro 80) which has a wide band frequency (200 kHz - 1 MHz), placed and coupled on the specimens with silicon oil (fig. 1). A high pass filter with 40 dB fixed gain preamplifier is used to obtain a total of 94 dB. In order to have the maximum sensivity during tests, a predetermined threshold is set providing a ring down count of 15-25 counts/h simply from the background noise but higher than the level of electronical and mechanical noises.

On-line AE apparatus measure the classical parameters. The total ring down cumulative counts and the amplitude distribution are recorded during the test.

Simultaneously with these treatments, the detected signals are amplified and conditioned and then digitized in Data Tab DL920 transient recorder with a memory of 4096-8 bit words and a sampling rate of $0.5 \mu\text{s}$. Thereafter, the data are transferred via an IEEE-488 bus to a computer for storage and post analysis.

The extent at which waveforms can be analysed, depends on the accuracy of signal recording and the facilities available for large-scale data storage and processing. Programs are developed for control data acquisition and signal processing. Note that the measurement conditions for each test are set in specified file (gain, cut-off frequency, sampling rate, full scale amplitude and detection threshold). Three types of waveform parameters (amplitude, frequency and energy) are computed as the features for each waveform. AE signals are complex and contain great of information; many studies [7,8,9] have been reported in which these parameters were used to discriminate between emission from different sources.

WAVEFORM ANALYSIS

Acoustic emission signals are processed by the following programs:

Cumulative count

The cumulative ring down count is the number of time of which signal amplitude exceed a limited threshold. The most used model is that one proposed by Harris and Dunegan [10]. They consider that AE waveform $V(t)$ can be defined by:

$$V(t) = V_o(t)e^{-\beta t} \quad (1)$$

$$V_o(t) = V_m \sin \omega t \quad (2)$$

V_m : maximum amplitude

β : parameter characterising of the specimen-transducer coupling

The cumulative count N is deduced by using the equations 1 and 2:

$$N = \frac{\omega}{2\pi} Ln \frac{V_m}{V_s} \quad (3)$$

N : ring down cumulative count
 V_m : maximum amplitude
 V_s : detection threshold

Amplitude distribution

Another feature (amplitude distribution), well adapted to the study of burst type signals, has been proposed by Pollock [11]. This parameter allows to determine the events number where the amplitude is superior to the threshold. He suggested a function of distribution $F(v)$ being used in normal or cumulative form on logarithmic scales. He proved that the parameter b representing the amplitude distribution can characterise the damage mechanism. A high value of b indicates a low acoustic activity characterised by a more narrow amplitude distribution. It is worth noting that a small value of b illustrates the presence of high amplitude emission.

$$F(v) = \left(\frac{V}{V_o} \right)^{-b} \quad (4)$$

V : detected signal amplitude
 V_o : lowest amplitude
 b : characteristic parameter of material

Time-domain

Each signal is examined to determine its shape and duration. The modulus of the voltage V_{ij} obtained for each "i" point in the waveform.

Frequency analysis

Features in the frequency domain are obtained by using a discrete Fast Fourier Transform subroutine in the analysis program. The fast Fourier transform of signal $X(t)$ is given by:

$$X(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} X(t) e^{-j2\pi ft} dt \quad (5)$$

$$X(f) = |X(f)| e^{-j\theta(f)} \quad (6)$$

$|X(f)|$: amplitude
 $\theta(f)$: phase

Power spectra $S_{xx}(f)$ in the frequency range is evaluated for each AE waveforms by:

$$S_{xx}(f) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} R_{xx}(\tau) e^{-j2\pi f\tau} d\tau \quad (7)$$

$R_{xx}(\tau)$: auto correlation function of $X(t)$

The mean power spectral density S_{moy} for n identical spectrum is computed as follow:

$$S_{moy} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n S_i(f) \quad (8)$$

Signal energy E is calculated by:
$$E = \sum_{f_1=f_1}^{f_2} S(f) \tag{9}$$
 $[f_1 - f_2]$: wide band frequency

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The damage mechanisms in these composite materials have been recently investigated by [4,5]. One can be observed that woven composites present two interfaces kinds (Fig. 1) called:
Interface 1: It's fibre/matrix interface inside the transverse bundle.
Interface 2: It's fibre/matrix interface localised between two bundles.

Figure 1. Interface kinds in woven composite materials.

It is clearly seen that the interface 1 from the ductile material XD8084.05/VT is better quality than that of the rigid matrix material D470.36/VT. Furthermore, the static rupture of ductile material is principally due to the interface 2 failure producing a catastrophic failure of this material.

This study permits to attribute for each range of amplitudes corresponding a determined damage process. Hence, the amplitude range of 40 to 55 dB has been attributed to the matrix cracking, while the range of 60 to 65 dB has been affected to the interface failure. Concerning the fibre pull-out phenomena, a range of 65 to 80 dB has been attributed. Finally, the amplitudes which are greater than 80 dB corresponds to fibre fracture.

The load-deflection curves show that the ductile material XD8084.05/VT indicates an abrupt drop of loading (around 90% of the rupture load). Whereas, the rigid matrix material D470.36/VT behaves a little loading drops (Fig.2).

Figure 2. Load/Events Nbr-displacement curves.

Both of the amplitude distribution (Fig. 3) and SEM observations have enabled to identify the principal damage mechanisms occurring in these materials.

Figure 3. Amplitude distribution .

The first damages, appeared on the ductile material XD8084.05/VT by the matrix micro cracking, are traduced in the form of EA amplitude distribution, localised in 40 to 60 dB range. Whereas, the rigid material presents, in addition, an amplitude signal around 65 dB (Fig. 3). Contrary to the precedent material, the microscopical observations have indicated the matrix cracking and micro cracking phenomena within the interface 1.

During this period, generated AE waveforms are also analysed. These results exhibit a low acoustic activity characterised by signals having a low amplitude and energy. This emission is essentially a continuous type which has frequency spectra with several components (Fig. 4) and can be found in the course of the mechanical test.

Figure 4. Typical continuous signal and frequency spectra of matrix cracking.

During the loading phase, the damage phenomena in the ductile material still practically identical with only an amplification of the phenomena which existed before. On the other hand, in the rigid material case, load-deflection curve shows a little drop of loading before the macroscopical rupture.

During this load unhook, we observe an increase acoustic emission activity identified by higher amplitude compared to that obtained during the first damage phase.

These AE waveforms are a burst type and their spectral frequency permitted to distinguish a principal component centred around 350 KHz (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. Burst type signal

An important modification of the amplitude distributions appears at the moment of the catastrophic failure of the ductile material with an appearance of a pick value around 65 dB. The fractographical observations of the failed specimens allow to attribute this pick to the interface 1 failure. The damages in the interface 1 are very limited and don't be able to explain the catastrophic rupture of the specimen. The fibre breaking is a phenomena taking place at the end of the loading test.

Concerning the rigid material, the modification of the amplitude distribution due to the macroscopic rupture is less remarkable than the shape of amplitude distribution in the case of the ductile material. The microscopical observations indicate that the damages exist in both interface 1 and 2 with fibre cracking standing in the tensile part of the specimen.

The analysis of recorded AE at the end of the test for both materials, indicates two types of remarkable signals. The first signals (Fig. 6a) which occurred at the beginning of the loading drop, have a similar aspect to those met before (Fig. 5) but with more important amplitude and an energy. It is of burst type and long duration with a component frequency adjusted around 350 kHz.

At this damage stage the more dominant phenomena to which this signal could be assigned, would be the interface failure or fibre-matrix friction.

The second type of signal (Fig. 6b) is recorded at the end of the mechanical test when the specimen is completely broken. This failure is characterised by the superposition on the acoustic signal produced by a mechanical vibration corresponding to the very low frequency component of the spectra.

This type of signal is short duration, with a predominant high frequency pick about 500 kHz could be generated by fibre breaking process taking place just after interface 2 failure.

Figure 6a. Typical signal associated with fibre-matrix friction.

Figure 6b. Signal and frequency spectra of fibre failure.

CONCLUSION

In the present work, the damage mechanisms in woven composite materials are investigated in three-point flexural tests. Signal processing of AE has been used in order to correlate between acoustic activity and rupture mechanisms well identified by SEM observations.

Results obtained for the both investigated materials are similar. The matrix cracking is correlated with the low amplitude signals which are could be classed from 40 to 55 dB. The mechanism source responsible of the fibre fracture is characterized by burst signals having a great amplitude and energy localised around 500 KHz.

Acoustic emission technique associated with scanning electron microscopy observations seems particularly well suited for studying and identifying damage mechanisms in composite materials. However, because the phenomena are complex, more advanced and appropriate analysis (such as pattern recognition or data analysis) are required to better characterize and discriminate failure processes.

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